
EFFECTS OF TRAINING OF ACADEMIC STAFF ON EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE IN FEDERAL POLYTECHNICS, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

This Study examines the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance in the Federal Polytechnics in Nigeria. The main objective is to examine the effects of Training of Academic Staff on: employees' Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality respectively. It is equally hypothesized that there's no significant effect of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality respectively. A structured, close-ended questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale was adopted to get data from the respondents. A total of 220 copies of the questionnaire were randomly administered using a stratified random sampling technique across the 7 schools as well as the library unit of the Polytechnic. Ordinary Least Square (O.L.S) method of regression and ANOVA methods of analysis were employed in analyzing the results with the aid of SPSS computer package. Findings revealed that the Training of Academic Staff has a significant effect on employees' productivity, enhanced timeliness in service delivery and work quality. The study recommends among other issues for the periodic re-training of staff bearing in mind the dynamics of human activities.

Keywords: Training; Performance; Productivity; Timeliness; Work Quality; Academic Staff.

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1. Introduction

Organizations are encountering increased competition owing to globalization, transformations in technology, political and economic environments (Evans, Pucik & Barsoux, 2002 cited in Tukunimulongo, 2016) and therefore prompting these organizations to train their employees as one of the ways to prepare them to adjust to the dynamics of time to enhance their performance becomes imperative (Tukunimulongo, 2016). It is important not to disregard the prevailing evidence on the development of knowledge in the business corporate world in the final ten. This maturation has not merely been conveyed about by improvements in technology nor a combination of factors of production but increased efforts towards growth of organizational human resources. It is, consequently, the duty of every organization to raise the business performance of the employees and certainly the implementation of training and growth is one of the major steps that

most companies need to accomplish this. As is evident that employees are a crucial resource, it is important to optimize the contribution of employees to the company's aims and goals as a means of maintaining effective public presentation. This demand for managers to confirm an acceptable provision of staff that is socially and technically capable and talented career development into high-quality departments or management positions (Sultana, Irum, Ahmed &Mehmood, 2012).

The interrogation that may originate in many instances is why human resources are significant. Having in mind that human resources are the intellectual property of the firm, employees prove to be a serious beginning of acquiring competitive advantage, according to Houger (2006), and training is the sole mode of developing organizational intellectual property through building employees' competencies. In parliamentary law to succeed, organizations have to obtain and apply human resources effectively (Houger, 2006). Organizations, therefore, need to design its human resources management in ways that fit into the organization's structure as this will make the organizations achieve their ends and targets. Moreover, it is too important for governing bodies to assist their work force in obtaining the necessary skills required and increase loyalty. The management of human resources in Africa in general and Nigeria in particular is quite challenging as most systems have difficulties seeing the correct gauge of human resources. This may partly be a consequence of the different kinds of problems, for instance, political instability, corruption, bureaucracy, inadequate infrastructure, low level of education of education and purchasing power, diseases and famine known to predominate in the African continent (Kamoche, 2002).

To build up the desired knowledge, skills and abilities of the employees, to perform well on the job, requires effective training plans that may also affect employee motivation and commitment (Asaju, 2008). In lodge to prepare their workers to perform their tasks as desired, organizations provide training so as to optimize their employees' potential. Most firms, by applying long term planning, invest in building new skills by their hands, enabling them to cope with the changeable conditions that they may confront in the future, therefore, improving the employees' performance through superior level of motivation and dedication. When employees know that their organization takes in interest in them through providing training programs, they in turn apply their best endeavors to accomplish organizational goals, and express high performance in their tasks.

Employees are the most valuable asset of any society or institution as they can establish or break a company's or institution's reputation and can adversely affect profitability or the accomplishment of set goals. Employees often are responsible for the large volume of the necessary work to be performed as well as customer satisfaction and the quality of products or services and events. Without proper training, employees, both novel and old do not receive the information and grow the skill sets necessary for achieving their jobs at their maximum voltage. Employees who undergo proper training tend to preserve their jobs longer than those who do not. Without training, employees do not hold a solid grip on their obligations or obligations. Employee training refers to plans that provide workers with information, new skills, or professional development opportunities.

According to Byrne (2011), managers are trying their very best to develop employees' capabilities, ultimately creating a good working environment within the organization. In order to match with the global educational standard in the Federal Polytechnics in Nigeria, the management is involved in developing effective training and educational plans for its academic staff members to outfit them

with the desired knowledge, sciences and abilities to accomplish institutional goals. This line of action by the top management would not only improve the academic staff performance, but also create positive image of the institution.

Thus, effective training programmes help the academic staff of the polytechnics to get acquainted with new technological advancements, and to gain full command of the competencies and skills required to perform at a particular job and to avoid on the job errors and mistakes. Amongst the important functions of human resources management, is employee development through proper training and development programmes. This study looks at the effects of Training of Academic staff on employees' Performance in Federal Polytechnics in Nigeria.

2. Statement of the Problem

The massive employment of staff in 2017/18 was unprecedented in the history of the Federal Polytechnic in Nigeria. The challenges posed by new employees can be very costly. The implication of such a line of action on the performances of the school was great to say the least. Many of the newly employed academic staff could not find their bearing in the roles expected of them. This led to poor student performance. Less than average performance of students in recent times, in spite of all the training programmes instituted by the schools with the aim of improving the academic staff quality was a matter of concern to all and sundry.

This study stems out of the realization of the need to examine the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' performance bearing in mind the huge amounts being invested in training programmes by the polytechnic over the years.

Furthermore, the inconsistency in the existing empirical literature (Abeeha&Bariha, 2012; Ahmed &Tsafe, 2013) makes it inevitable to seek for more evidences on the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance in the Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria.

The lacuna created by the non-contextualization of the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance with specific reference to Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria, will be bridged by this study.

3. Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda. The specific objectives are to:

- 1) Examine the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Productivity in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria.
- 2) Assess the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Timeliness in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria.
- 3) Evaluate the effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Work quality in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria.

4. Statement of the Hypotheses

Based on the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are postulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Productivity in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Timeliness in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant effect of Training of Academic staff on employees' Work quality in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria.

5. Concept of Training

Efficient preparation and growth plans are targeted at improving the employees' performances. Training refers to bridging the gap between the current performance and the standard desired performance. Training could be given through different methods such as on the job coaching and mentoring, peer cooperation and participation by the underlings. This team work enable employees actively participate on the job and produces better public presentation, hence improving organizational functioning. Training programs not only develops employees, but also help an organization to make full usage of their human resources in favor of acquiring competitive advantage. Thus, it seems mandatory for the firm to plan for such a training program for its employees to raise their abilities and competencies that are demanded at the workplace, (Deborah &Ofori, 2006).

According to Waleed (2011), as cited in Ng'ethe, (2014) training is not merely a way of arming employees with the skills they require to execute their jobs it is often deemed to be representative of an employer's commitment to their work force. Nevertheless, it is significant to point out that human resources (HR) practices work to develop individual knowledge and sciences, as well as employee attitude and behaviors. If these effects are prevalent enough in the employees' population, then the collective changes in human capital, attitudes, behaviors and associated organizational climate would be substantial enough to influence organizational performance (Eleve, 2012).

Training not only builds up the capacities of the employee, but sharpen their thinking ability and creativity in order to create more beneficial decisions in time and in a more productive manner (Harvey, 2002). Moreover, it also enables employees to deal with the customer in an effective manner and respond to their complaints in time (Harvey, Myers &Novicevic, 2002). The training develops self-efficacy and results in superior performance on jobs (Svenja, 2007), by substituting the traditional employment practices by efficient and effective work-related practices (Kathiravan, Devadason&Zakkeer, 2006). Training refers to a planned intervention aimed at enhancing the factors of individual task performance (Chiaburu&Tekleab, 2005).

5.1. Importance of Training

Training is important and an imperative tool for the organization to revamp the operation of all the personnel for organizational growth and success (Svenja, 2007). It is useful to both employers and employees of an organization. An employee will become more efficient and productive if he is

coached well. Organizations can improve and increase the quality of the existing employees by offering thorough preparation and growth. Training is essential not just to increase productivity but also to propel and inspire workers by letting them recognize how important their tasks are and giving them all the data they require to do those jobs (Herman & Kurt, 2016). The overall benefits obtained from employee training are: increased motivation, increased job satisfaction and morale, increased efficiencies in processes, resulting in financial gain, increased capacity to take on new technologies and methods, increased innovation in strategies and products and reduced employee turnover.

5.2. Methods of Training

Jackson (2002) noted that all the human resources development activities are meant to either improve performance on the present job of the individual, train new skills for a new job or a new position in the future and general growth for both individuals and organization so as to be able to meet an organization's current and future objectives. There are generally two different methods that organizations may select from for training and developing skills of its employees. These are on-the-job training given to organizational employees while taking their regular study at the same working venues and off-the-job training involves taking employees away from their usual work environments and therefore the trainees concentrates on the preparation. Models of the on-the-job training include, but are not limited to, job rotations and transfers, coaching and or mentoring. On the other hand, *off-the-job training* examples include: conferences, role playing, and many more. Armstrong (2013) argues that on-the-job training may consist of teaching or coaching by more experienced people or trainers at the desk or at the bench. Different organizations are motivated to carry on different training methods for a number of reasons for example; (1) depending on the organization's strategy, goals and resources available, (2) depending on the needs identified at the time, and (3) the target group to be trained which may include among others individual workers, groups, teams, department or the integral system.

5.3. Job Rotation and Transfers

Job rotation and transfers according to Jeremic, Jovanovic and Gasevi (2003), is a means of developing employee skills within the system and involves movements of employees from one official duty to another, for example, demanding along the higher rank position within the system, or from one branch of the organization to another. For transfers, for instance, it could affect movement of employees from one nation to another. These rotations and transfers facilitate employees to gain knowledge of the different operations within the organization together with the differences existing in different nations where the establishment works. The knowledge acquired by the selected employees for this method is beneficial to the system as it may increase the competitive advantage of the system.

5.4. Concept of Employee Performance

According to Hawthorne studies and many other research works on the productivity of workers, highlighted the fact that employees who are gratified with their jobs will experience higher job performance, and thus supreme job retention, than those who are not happy with their jobs (Irene, 2009). Moreover, it is stated that employees are more likely to turnover if they are not satisfied

and thus less motivated to demonstrate good performance. Employee performance is higher in happy and satisfied workers and the management finds it comfortable to motivate high performers to attain firm targets. (Kinicki&Kreitner; 2007) The employee could be only met when they feel themselves competent to do their jobs, which is accomplished through better training plans.

5.5. Relationship between Training and Employees' Performance

Most of the previous studies provide the evidence that there is a strong positive relationship between human resource management practices and organizational performance (Purcell, Kinnie, Hutchinson, Rayton& Swart, 2003). According to Michael (2008), mentioned in his study that training and maturation program, as unitary of the vital human resources management practice, positively affects the character of the workers' knowledge, skills and capability and thus results in higher employee performance on the task. This relationship ultimately leads to superior organizational performance. The outcome of a study by Mona, Iravo and Omondi (2011), describes the positive correlation between preparation and employee performance as being=. 233. Therefore, we can predict from this finding that it is not possible for the firm to make higher returns without properly using its human resources. This can only occur when a firm is able to meet its employees' job related demands in a timely fashion. Training is the solitary manner of identifying the deprived need of employees and then building their required competence level and then that they may do well to accomplish organizational goals. Studies by Sultan, el tal (2012), conducted in the telecom sector of Pakistan, states the R^2 as.501 which means that 50.1% of variation in employee performance is brought by training programs. Furthermore, the T-value was 8.58 that explain training is the best predictor of employee performance. As depicted by the work of Harrison (2000), learning through training influence the organizational performance by greater employee performance, and is supposed to be a central element in the accomplishment of corporate goals. Nevertheless, implementing training programs as a solution to covering performance issues such as occupying the crack between the criterion and the actual performance is an effectual means of improving employee performance (Swart, et tal, 2005).

According to Swart, Mann, Brown and Price (2005), bridging the performance gap refers to carrying out a relevant training intervention for the sake of acquiring particular skills and abilities of the workers and enhancing employee performance. He further refines the concept by stating that training facilitates organization to realize that its actors are not performing well and a thus their knowledge, skills and attitudes needs to be shaped according to the firm demands. At that place might be several causes for poor performance of the employees such as workers may not feel motivated anymore to apply their competencies, or perhaps not convinced enough in their capabilities, or they may be facing work-life conflict. Altogether the above aspects must be weighed by the firm while selecting most appropriate training intervention that assists organizations to resolve all problems and enhance employee motivational levels to participate and meet firm expectations by showing desired performance. As mentioned by Swart, et al., (2005), thus employee, superior performance occur only because of good quality breeding programs that leads to employee motivation and their needs met. Wright and Gary (2001) noted that employee competencies change through efficient preparation plans. It not only betters the overall operation of the employees to effectively do the current job, but also enhance the knowledge, skills and attitude of the workers necessary for the future job, hence contributing to superior organizational

performance. Through training the employee competencies are built up and enable them to implement job related work efficiently, and achieve firm objectives in a competitive way.

Yet, employee performance is likewise regarded by some environmental elements such as corporate culture, organizational structure, task design, performance appraisal systems, power and politics prevailing in the firm and the group dynamics. If the above mentioned problems exist at the firm, employee performance decreases not due to lack of relevant knowledge, accomplishments and attitude, merely because of the above mentioned hurdles. To make training effective and to ensure positive effect of training on employee performance these elements should be taken into consideration (Wright & Gray 2001). Lisa and Holly (2007), stated that workers feel more given to the firm, when they feel an organizational commitment towards them and thus show higher performance.

Kum, Cowded and Karodia (2014), reports that there is a positive correlation between effective training program and employee productivity, all the same, to make it possible, Swart, et al., (2005), said it is the duty of the managers to identify the factors that hinders training program effectiveness and should call for necessary measures to counteract their effect on employee performance. In addition, Kamoche, Yaw, Frank and Gerry (2004) reasoned that high degrees of employee commitment are achieved if training, achieves learning outcomes and improves the public presentation, both on private and organizational level. These determinations are too coherent with the results of Kim's (2006) research work. More often than not, it can be argued that the result of the training program on employee issues such as motivation, job satisfaction and organizational loyalty, did not pick up much care thus far. A rare work was performed to examine whether firms can affect their workers' attitude, through proper training interventions. According to Nome (2010), training should be projected in such a way that examined effects in organizational commitment. On the other hand Gaertner and Nollen (2009) proposed that employees' commitment is a result of more or less human resources practices, that is, succession planning and promotions, career development and breeding opportunities. All these exercises, when achieved results in greater employee performance. Moreover, Meyer and Smith (2000) the link between human resource management practices and organizational commitment, thus as to find out the causal agents of effective employee performance.

Although the above literature provides the evidences regarding the benefits of training and its positive influence on employee performance, Cheramie, et al., (2007), argued that, management most at times feel hesitant while investing in its human resources due to diverse causes. Sometimes, in spite of receiving effective and timely training programs, some employees try to grab it for the sake of their own market value and employment opportunity or willing to change jobs but because of higher salaries, and thus, firm investment in training outcomes as a cost rather than net income. It is likewise noted that due to the resistance of the organization towards offering training, this will compel individuals to invest in themselves for their career growth and greater performance (Baruch, 2006).

As mentioned by Ngome (2010), training sessions accelerate the initiative, ability and creativity of the work force and facilitate to avoid human resource obsolescence that may happen because of demographic factors such as age, attitude or the inability to cope with alterations. Obisi (2001), reported that training is a systematic process of enhancing the knowledge, skills and attitude, so

leads to satisfactory performance by the employees at work. He further observed that the need and objectives of the training program should be identified before offering it to the employees.

Kraak, (2005), argued that training is the crux of better organizational management, as it makes employees more efficient and effectual. They further elaborated that training practices have a strong bond with all other human resources practices as postulated by Kamoche, (2002), it enables employees to grow themselves within the firm and raise their market value in the marketplace. Moreover, training supports to shape the employees' job related behavior and help them to take part in the achiever of the organization and at long last the firm gets higher return due to the superior functioning of its employees. Kraak (2005) further noted that a well-educated actor is able to get the best usage of organizational resources along with a minimal level of wastages. As stated by Niazi (2011), when employees are well trained organization can designate responsibility and authority to them with full confidence of ensuring organizational success.

Rao (2011) suggests the need for renewed attention to employee training due to its ability to cut costs and reduce performance shortfalls in organizations. It has been proven on countless occasions that, there is a strong link between various training and development practices and organizational performance (Raja,Furgan, & Muhammad, 2011). Research has found training as a tool for cost cutting and value creation in organizations (Kraak, 2005, Gadi & Kee, 2018b). Similarly, training facilitates the achievement of corporate strategy and improves organizational performance, especially for learning organizations (Quarty, 2012). So training must be aligned with organizational strategy in order to result in high performance in those organizations. Farther, a written report focusing on the impact of training on organizational performance reveals that, only off-the job training improves performance, whereas on-the-job training does not (Kamoche, 2002). Additionally, Gareth (2003) argued that, general training has a positive impact on firm performance, whereas firm-specific training does not.

Often in implicit findings, Niazi, (2011), argued that training increases employees' propensity to perform and subsequently contributes to the firms' performance. For example,Rao (2011), was of the view that those companies (citing Jaguar Cars; Lucas Industries; IBM; Marks & Spencer; British steel; & Nissan) that integrated training and development practices into their business planning enhances their own performance. A study by Niazi (2011) revealed that organizations that are committed to quality investment in training and development of its employees receive an exponential growth in customer delights, profitability and overall economic growth of those organizations. There is a huge return on those training investments (ROI). Gereth (2003), supported Niazi (2011) by adding that, those organizations that train employees reduce employee turnover rate. Kraak (2005), citing Bishop (1994), indicates that employer-provided training and development raises subjective productivity and performance measure by almost 16%.

Moreover, the above empirical findings suggest that organizations that train their employees consistently have better outcomes than those that do not(Gadi & Kee, 2018a). Quarty (2012) agreeing to the finding of Niazi (2011) indicates that training can be a powerful driving force for firm expansion as well as building capabilities too, and subsequently firms' profitability and productivity. In exploring the impact of training on enterprise growth, Jones, Richard, Paul and Peter (2008) confirms that increasing training efforts increases firms' growth in terms of sales volumes and revenues. In contrast, empirical findings on training and organizational performance

are inconclusive. As some scholars bemoaned that, training does not necessarily impact performance. One divergent view comes from Kraak (2005) who found that the relationship between employee training and organizational performance is not significant. Other researchers like Niazi (2011), and Gaertner and Nollen (2009), also argued that there is a weak direct relationship between training and firm's performance. Obisi (2001), also claims that, training activities fail to influence the firm's performance because the activities are not linked to the firm's strategic plans. However, whether there is a strong or a weak link between these two concepts requires further contextual and empirical findings especially for industries and institutions in Nigeria.

In the improvement of groups, training plays a crucial role, improving overall performance in addition to increasing productivity, and subsequently setting groups within the fine role to face competition and live at the top. This approach that there is a giant difference among the agencies that trains their personnel and groups that do not (Benedictta&Appiah, 2010, Dang & Gadi, 2013). Training is a kind of interest which is deliberate, systematic and it effects in a greater degree of skill, information and competency which might be necessary to perform paintings successfully (Kraak 2005). There exists a high-quality association among education and employee performance. Training generates blessings for the worker as well as for the company by means of positively influencing worker performance through the improvement of employee expertise, skills, capacity, competencies and conduct (Rao, 2011).

In the real world, organizational increase and improvement is suffering from a number of factors. In line with the prevailing studies throughout the improvement of businesses, worker schooling performs an essential function in improving overall performance in addition to increasing productiveness. This in turn ends in putting organizations within the quality positions to stand opposition and live at the pinnacle. This therefore implies the lifestyles of an enormous distinction between the agencies that educate their employees and organizations that do not. Existing literature provides evidence of the lifestyles of the obvious consequences of schooling and development on worker overall performance. Some studies have proceeded by way of looking at overall performance in terms of employee performance particularly (Purcell, Kinnie& Hutchinson 2003; Harrison 2000), even as others have prolonged it to a standard outlook of organizational performance (Dessler, 1997; Swart, et al., 2005, Gadi, Silas, & Macrop, 2015). In one way or the alternative, the two are related inside the feel that employee overall performance is a characteristic of organizational performance since worker performance affects widespread organizational overall performance. In relation to the above, Wright and Geroy (2001), stated that employee skills trade through powerful training packages. It therefore not simplest improves the general performance of the personnel to effectively carry out their current jobs, but also complements the knowledge, capabilities and mind-set of the workers important for the destiny jobs, therefore contributing to advanced organizational performance.

Earlier research on training and employee overall performance has found interesting findings concerning this courting. Training has been validated to generate overall performance improvement associated blessings for the employee in addition to for the organization by using positively influencing employee performance via the improvement of worker expertise, capabilities, capacity, talents and behavior (Benedictta & Appiah, 2010; Harrison, 2000). Moreover, other studies, for instance, one through Swart, et al., (2005) problematic on education

as a method of managing skill deficits and performance gaps as a path of enhancing employee performance. According to Swart, et al., (2005), bridging the performance hole refers to enforcing an applicable training intervention for the sake of growing particular abilities and skills of the employees and enhancing worker overall performance. They further intricate the idea by means of declaring that schooling helps corporations to recognize that its workers aren't appearing well and as such their knowledge, skills and attitudes wishes to be molded in line with the company wishes. It is constantly in order that employees own a positive amount of knowledge related to one of a kind jobs. However, it is vital to notice that this isn't always enough and personnel want to constantly adapt to new necessities of activity performance. In other phrases, corporations want to have non-stop rules of schooling and retraining of personnel and as such do now not want to await occurrences of ability and overall performance gaps.

According to Wright and Geroy (2001), worker competencies exchange through powerful training programs. It no longer only improves the overall operation of the employees to successfully do the contemporary business, but also beautifies the understanding, abilities and mindset of the people essential for the destiny activity, for that reason contributing to advanced organizational overall performance. Through schooling, employee capabilities are developed and permit them to put into effect the task associated work effectively, and reap company goals in an aggressive manner. Further nonetheless, dissatisfaction, court cases, absenteeism and turnover may be significantly decreased while personnel are so properly educated that they are able to revel in the direct delight associated with the experience of achievement and knowledge that they are growing their inherent capabilities (Kim, 2006).

Akeke, Akeke, and Awolusi (2015) said that an extensive courting turned into determined among the worker training and their resultant performance in undertaking extraordinary obligations. It became found that the ones employees who've taken trainings were extra successful in performing unique assignment and vice versa. Training has an instantaneous courting with the personnel' job performance. Similar findings had been suggested by way of (Singh & Kassa, 2012; Singh, 2017).

However, Chaudhary and Rangnekar (2017)posited that while schooling is a thing in task overall performance, it's miles the combination of factors which includes working surroundings, employee abilities and information, motivation and rewards, conversation flow and organizational subculture that significantly improve personnel' overall performance. Herman and Kurt (2016), argued that worker schooling equip employees with competencies that enable them to become greater efficient and productive workers. Furthermore, personnel who're well-skilled frequently have higher motivation and morale because they sense that the company has invested of their capability and development. This also consequences in decrease turnover fees. Yamoah (2013), determined that trained personnel often paintings better as groups because anyone is aware about the expectancies and can obtain them together easily. Trained employees are also extra assured of their performance and selection-making skills. In addition, personnel who get hold of normal schooling are much more likely to simply accept change and give you new ideas.

Employees who learn new capabilities via training make desirable candidates for promotions due to the fact they have shown their capacity to learn, preserve and use facts. Reliable, professional personnel can also be empowered to educate different personnel, the fact that reduces strain for the management crew. Because of the real implications of schooling, it is crucial to have education

this is powerful. Studies have demonstrated that greater costly, however powerful education can store money this is wasted on reasonably-priced, but inefficient education (Kenney, 2009).

Latif, Jan, and Shaheen (2013) found four subscales to have a significant contribution towards the formation of an effective preparation program. The survey identified four components to be contingent to an effective training, they were: Satisfaction with the training session, Training content satisfaction, Trainee satisfaction, and Transfer of learning.

Kennedy (2009) found that the frequency of training received has an impact on business performance. After examining information from employees of the Judicial Service of Ghana, he described that many employees associated frequent in-service training with improved business performance. Similarly, Ribeiro and Semedo (2014), found a substantial relationship between frequent on-the-job training and employees' performance. He said that frequently training employees resulted in employees taking in fewer errors, causing more work performed in a caved in time period and managers spending less time on supervision of employees.

However, Philips (2006), argued that loss of common training isn't necessarily the cause of below-performance of personnel. He said they want to decide whether a trouble may be solved via schooling. Whenever employees are not acting their jobs well, its miles regularly assumed that education will convey them up to traditional. This is not usually the case. For example, training is less powerful for issues springing up from an employee's lack of motivation or lack of interest to the task. Similarly, Daniels (2010) posited that education is not a panacea; it cannot get rid of core troubles like low capitalization or a product line that doesn't meet clients' wishes. Although education can offer brilliant improvements in the organization, the key to getting the exceptional return on investment from training is to view it strategically instead of tactically. Adeniji (2002), in addition said that schooling reduces worker turnover and promotes purpose congruency whilst loss of education will increase absenteeism rate, low output, negative nice and results in high unit cost.

Despite the significance of training and manpower development in employee productivity and organizational performance, education programs aren't sufficiently supported via companies in Nigeria. These corporations keep in mind the cash they will spend on their education applications as waste instead of a funding. They fail to foresee the desirability of continuous schooling and improvement in their personnel if you want to sell the efficiency and effectiveness in their companies. Those that try and conduct trainings for their employees accomplish that in an ad-hoc and haphazard manner, and as such, schooling in the ones businesses is greater or less unplanned and unsystematic. This view is corroborated by Nwachukwu (1988), who argued that many personnel have failed in organizations because of lack of simple education.

6. Theoretical Framework

There have been numerous theories propounded to explain the relevance of schooling desires in any status quo or employer. In social getting to know idea, personnel acquire new abilities and know-how by means of observing other members of the group of workers whom they have faith in and as properly trust to be credible and greater informed. The aid-based view (RBV) of the firm encouraged that an organization can gain competitive benefit by means of attracting and preserving

competent human resources and as well perceives applicable education for them on the way to hold improving their potential for most excellent overall performance. By implication, the effectiveness of schooling and mastering depends on the pattern of the task associated knowledge, competencies, functionality, talents and behavior which might be vital for more overall performance which always is able to influencing organizational fulfillment.

7. Research Design

The descriptive research design was used as a means of assessing the effects of Training of Academic Staff on employees' Performance in the Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria.

7.1. Population and Sampling Technique

The population of the study is the 410 Academic staff of the Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda. Yamane's (1973) sample size determination formula was used to determine the desired sample size of the research work.

Given the survey population (N) of 410, and making an allowance for error of 5 per cent, the sample size is determined at approximately 203 as worked below:

$$s = \frac{N}{1+N(ME)^2}$$

$$= \frac{410}{1+410(0.05)^2} = \frac{410}{2.025} = 203$$

Then, a stratified random sampling procedure was used to select the sample across the schools and the library unit that constitute the academic segments of the Polytechnic. The table below presents the stratified sample size randomly drawn from each of the 7 schools and the library unit.

Table 1: Population and Sample Size

Schools in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria	Population	Sample Size
School of Business and Management Studies (SBMS)	83	45
School of Engineering and Technology (SET)	56	30
School of Environmental Studies (SES)	37	20
School of Science and Technology (SST)	73	39
School of Information and Communication Technology (SICT)	66	35
School of General Studies (SGS)	70	38
School of Remedial and Basic Studies (SRBS)	17	09
Library Unit	8	04
TOTAL	410	220

Source; Establishment Office/ Researchers' Computation, 2016

7.2. Methods of Data Collection

This study utilized primary data collected basically through structured closed ended questionnaires of 5-point Likert scale format administered to the academic staff of the Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda. Using a stratified random sampling method, 220 copies of the questionnaire were administered among the academic staff members of the Polytechnic. Out of this figure 205 were completed and returned, giving a response rate of 93.2%. The responses received are presented and analyzed below. The spread of the 205 completed and returned copies of the questionnaire is presented in table 3 it is imperative to state that secondary data were obtained from the Polytechnic's bulletins as well as records within the establishment unit.

Table 2: Completed and Returned copies of questionnaire.

Schools in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda, Nigeria	Completed Questionnaire
School of Business and Management Studies (SBMS)	42
School of Engineering and Technology (SET)	28
School of Environmental Studies (SES)	18
School of Science and Technology (SST)	36
School of Information and Communication Technology (SICT)	33
School of General Studies (SGS)	36
School of Remedial and Basic Studies (SRBS)	08
Library Unit	04
TOTAL	205

Source; Researchers' Computation 2016

Table 3: Scale Reliability of Independent Variables

Concept/Independent Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Enhancement	0.92
Job Knowledge	0.87
Skills	0.91
Competence	0.89
Morale	0.78

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2016

Table 3 above revealed that all the variables have Alpha Values above 0.6 mark recommended by Sekaran (2001). Therefore, all the variables in the instrument are deemed reliable.

Table 4: Scale Reliability of Dependent Variables

Concept/Dependent Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Productivity	0.88
Timeliness	0.93
Work Quality	0.81

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2016

Table 4 above further revealed that all the variables have Alpha Values above 0.6 mark recommended by Sekaran (2001). Therefore, all the variables in the instrument are deemed as highly reliable. The researcher decided to continue with the study.

7.3. Procedures for Data Analysis and Model Specifications

Ordinary Least Squares Method of Regression was used with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to determine and analyze the effects of academic staff training on employees' performance. Thus, training was measured by Enhancement, Job knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale as independent variables. The employee's performance was measured by Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality as dependent variables.

The Models for the Regression are:

PRDTY=F (Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence, Morale)

TIMLNS=F (Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence, Morale)

WQTY=F (Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence, Morale)

Mathematically,

$PRDTY = b_0 + \beta_1 \text{Enhancement} + \beta_2 \text{JobKnowledge} + \beta_3 \text{Skills} + \beta_4 \text{Competence} + \beta_5 \text{Morale} + \mu$

$TIMLNS = b_0 + \beta_1 \text{Enhancement} + \beta_2 \text{JobKnowledge} + \beta_3 \text{Skills} + \beta_4 \text{Competence} + \beta_5 \text{Morale} + \mu$

$WQTY = b_0 + \beta_1 \text{Enhancement} + \beta_2 \text{JobKnowledge} + \beta_3 \text{Skills} + \beta_4 \text{Competence} + \beta_5 \text{Morale} + \mu$

Where:

PRDTY=Productivity

TIMLNS=Timeliness

WQTY=Work Quality

b_0 =Intercept or Constant

β = Slope of the regression line with respect to the independent variables

μ =error term

7.4. Decision Rule

In order to estimate the regression analysis model, SPSS was used. The procedure involved specifying the independent and dependent variables; in this case, training (Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence, and Morale) are the independent variables while employees' performance (Productivity, Timeliness, and Work quality) are the dependent variables. SPSS was run and from the output, the values of the constant (b_0), coefficient of regression (β_1 - β_5) were obtained. In addition, the outputs showed the T statistics and P- values for the coefficients which resulted in either rejecting or failure to reject the hypotheses at 5% level of significance. The P-value is a probability of getting a result that is at least extremely as the critical values. The null hypotheses were rejected if the P-value is less than or equal to the critical value. Also, the outputs showed the coefficient of determination (r^2), which measured the proportion of the dependent variables that can be explained by the regression model. At the P-value of less than or equal to critical value the null hypothesis was rejected that there is a slope between the variables. The linear relationship exists when the P-value or significance level is less than or equal to the critical value.

8. Data Presentation and Analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.963 ^a	.687	.563	2.38432

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	171.422	5	28.255	24.347	.000 ^a
	Residual	105.401	199	1.176		
	Total	276.823	204			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.
b. Dependent Variable: Productivity.

Summary of Regression Results and other Statistics						
Regression	A	β_1 Enhancmnt	β_2 JobKnw	β_3 Skills	β_4 Competence	β_4 Morale
Coefficient	-3.025	0.201	0.423	0.563	0.432	1.324
P. value	0.000	0.022	0.002	0.021	0.023	0.001
R	0.687					
r ²	0.563					

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2016.

The regression line $\text{Productivity} = -3.025 + 0.201\text{Enhancement} + 0.423\text{JobKnowledge} + 0.563\text{Skills} + 0.432\text{Competence} + 1.324\text{Morale}$, indicates that employees' productivity will increase by 0.201units for every 1unit increase in Enhancement, increase by 0.423 units for every 1unit increase in Job Knowledge, increase by 0.563 units for every 1unit increase in Skills, increase by 0.432units for every 1unit increase in Competence, and increase by 1.324units for every 1unit increase in Morale. The significant values or P-values of 0.022, 0.004, 0.021, 0.023, and 0.001, in all the respective variables are less than the t-value of 0.05. We, thus, reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the Alternative Hypothesis, that the effect of training of the academic staff on employees' productivity of Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda is significant. This is collaborated by the correlation coefficient (r) of 0.963 that indicates a strong positive relationship. The coefficient of determination (r²) of 0.687 indicates that 68.7% of variation on employees' productivity can be explained by staff training. In the absence of training, it is indicated that employees' productivity will reduce by 3.025 as shown by the constant (α). The F-Statistics value of 24.347 and its corresponding P-value of 0.000 also collaborate the rejection of the null hypothesis that the model is fit and the effects of Training of Academic staff on Employees' Productivity is insignificant.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.801a	.821	.741	.76543

Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	104.435	5	18.465	12.435	.0021a
	Residual	169.759	198	2.118		
	Total	274.194	203			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.
b. Dependent Variable: Timeliness.

Summary of Regression Results and other Statistics						
Regression	A	β_1 Enhancmnt	β_2 JobKnw	β_3 Skills	β_4 Competence	β_4 Morale
Coefficient	-1.981	0.672	0.541	0.731	0.352	1.963
P. value	0.002	0.025	0.0098	0.034	0.022	0.0011
R	0.821					
r ²	0.741					

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2016.

The regression line $Timeliness = -1.981 + 0.672Enhancement + 0.541JobKnowledge + 0.731kills + 0.352Competence + 1.963Morale$ indicates that employees’ timeliness will increase by 0.672units for every 1unit increase in Enhancement, increase by 0.541units for every 1unit increase in Job Knowledge, increase by 0.731units for every 1unit increase in Skills, increase by 0.352units for every 1unit increase in Competence, and increase by 1.963units for every 1unit increase in Morale. The significant values or P-values of 0.025, 0.0098, 0.034, 0.022, and 0.0011, in all the respective variables are less than the t-value of 0.05. We therefore reject the Null Hypothesis and accept the Alternative hypothesis, that the effect of the Training of Academic staff on employees’ Timeliness in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda is significant. This is collaborated by the correlation coefficient (r) of 0.801 that indicates a strong positive relationship. The coefficient of determination (r²) of 0.821 indicates that about 82.1% of variation on employees’ timeliness can be explained by staff training. In the absence of staff training, it is indicated that employees’ timeliness will reduce by 1.981 as shown by the constant (α). The F-Statistics value of 12.435 and its corresponding P-value of 0.0021 also collaborate the rejection of the null hypothesis that the model is fit and the effect of Training of Academic Staff on employees’ Timeliness is insignificant.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.945a	.934	.812	1.3432

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	182.698	5	43.327	102.652	.0001a
	Residual	179.375	198	1.447		
	Total	362.073	203			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Enhancement, Job Knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale.
Dependent Variable: Work Quality.

Summary of Regression Results and other Statistics						
Regression	A	B ₁ Enhancmnt	B ₂ JobKmw	β ₃ Skills	β ₄ Competence	β ₄ Morale
Coefficient	-2.562	0.444	0.3423	2.342	0.343	1.334
P. value	0.000	0.002	0.021	0.030	0.005	0.010
R	0.934					
r ²	0.812					

Source: Researcher's Computation 2016.

The regression line $Work\ Quality = -2.562 + 0.444Enhancement + 0.342JobKnowledge + 2.342Skills + 0.343Competence + 1.334Morale$ indicates that employees' quality of work will increase by 0.444units for every 1unit increase in Enhancement, increase by 0.342units for every 1unit increase in Job Knowledge, increase by 2.342units for every 1unit increase in Skills, increase by 0.343 units for every 1 unit increase in Competence, and increase by 1.334units for every 1unit increase in Morale. The significant values or P-values of 0.002, 0.021, 0.030, 0.005, and 0.010, in all the respective variables are less than the t-value of 0.05. We, therefore, reject the Null hypothesis and accept the Alternative hypothesis that the effect of the Training of Academic staff on employees' Work quality in the Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda is significant. This is collaborated by the correlation coefficient (r) of 0.972 that indicates a strong positive relationship. The coefficient of determination (r²) of 0.934 indicates that about 93.4% of variation on employees' work quality can be explained by academic staff training. In the absence of such staff training, it is indicated that employees' work quality will reduce by 2.562 as shown by the constant (α). The F-Statistics value of 102.652 and its corresponding P-value of 0.0001 also collaborate the rejection of the Null hypothesis that the effect of the Training of Academic staff on employees' Work quality is insignificant.

9. Findings

From the above results and analyses, it is evident that, employees' performance in terms of Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality are positively related to Training of Academic Staff with statistical significance measured by employees' Enhancement, Job knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale. This implies that, employees' Productivity, Timeliness and Work quality increase with increase in Training of Academic staff such as employees' Enhancement, Job knowledge, Skills, Competence and Morale. This is consistent with the findings in previous studies such as Harrison (2000); Wright and Geroy (2001); Swart, et al., (2005); Farooq and Aslam (2011); and more recently Sultana, et al., (2012). Furthermore, the study aligns with the theory of reinforcement that believed that training is a strategic tool to make job interesting to the workers and as the avenue for the employees to improve themselves for optimal performance, which can

culminate to promoting employees for outstanding performance, innovation, and creativity as a result of the training attended. Thus, by implication, the effectiveness of training and learning depends on the pattern of the job related knowledge, skills, capability, competencies and behavior that are important for better performance which invariably is capable of influencing organizational success.

The overall results and analyses clearly indicate that, employees' performance in terms of productivity, timeliness and work quality is positively related with the Training of Academic Staff with statistical significance measured by employees' enhancement, job knowledge, skills, competence and morale respectively. The correlation coefficient (r) indicates a strong positive relationship between the variables of the study (Training of Academic Staff and Employees' Performance). The coefficients of determination (r^2) across the variables indicate that more than 80% of variation on employees' performance can be explained by staff training. The F-statistics indicated the fitness of the model in all the respective cases.

10. Conclusion

The findings of the study revealed positive and significant effects of the Training of Academic Staff on Employees' Performance in the Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda. This implies that effective academic staff training in terms of employees' enhancement, job knowledge, skills, competence, and morale, improve employees' performance in terms of productivity, timeliness, and work quality. Thus the study concludes that academic staff training in Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamodahas a significant effect in influencing the performances of employees. In another vein with regards to the regression results and analyses it was noted that employees' morale has greater influence in ensuring effective performance in terms of productivity, timeliness and work quality to other variables used in the study. Finally, skill was found to be the second most influential variable, followed by job knowledge, competence, and enhancement respectively.

11. Recommendations

In the light of the above findings and conclusion drawn, the study recommends that:

- 1) Federal Polytechnic, KauraNamoda should continue to train its academic staff in order to achieve the best performance from employees that will make the attainment of the overall objectives of the Polytechnic possible.
- 2) The current practice of paying trainees in bulk should be reviewed and made annually after submission of progress report to the institution. This will go a long way in minimizing inherent abuses now prevalent in the operation of training and development system in the Polytechnic.
- 3) Beneficiaries of training programmes should be required to serve the Polytechnic for a longer period before further sponsorship is made or being allowed to leave the service.
- 4) Officers sponsored for part-time programmes should be bonded by the polytechnic.
- 5) The polytechnic should endeavor to ascertain the status of the various training institutions in which its staff intend to go, before they are released for sponsorship.
- 6) Re-training of already trained staff should be periodically organized so as to spring up the desired employees' performance that will inspire better institutional performance and service delivery.

References

- [1] Abang, A. M., May-Chiun, L., & Maw, K. L., (2009). "Human Resource Practices and Organizational Performance. Incentives as Moderators". *Journal of Academic Research in Economics Vol1(2)*.
- [2] Abeeha, B. & Bariha, F (2012). "Effects of Employees Training On The Organizational Competitive Advantage: Empirical study of Private Sector of Islamabad, Pakistan" *Far East Journal of Psychology and Business. Vol6 (1)*.
- [3] Afshan, S., Sobia, I., Kamran, A. & Nasir, M. (2012) Impact of Training on Employees Performance: A Study of Telecommunication Sector in Pakistan *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business. Vol 4, No 6*.
- [4] Ahmed, A.I. & Tsafe, A.M. (2013) Impact of Employee Training on Organisation Efficiency, Enugu: *International Conference on Humanities, Science and Sustainable Development*.
- [5] Armstrong, M. (2006). *A Handbook of Human Resources Management Practice*, London, UK: Kogan Page, Ltd.
- [6] Armstrong, M. (2009). *A Handbook of Human Resources Management Practice*, (10th ed.), London: Kogan Page Limited.
- [7] Armstrong, M. (2010). *A Handbook of Human Resources Management Practice*, (11th ed.), London: Kogan Page Limited.
- [8] Armstrong, M. (2013). *A Handbook of Human Resources Management Practice*, (13th ed.), London: Kogan Page Limited.
- [9] Asaju K. (2008). Manpower Training and Development: An Essential Tool for Achieving Organizational Goals, *Journal of management and enterprise development Vol. 5(2)*
- [10] Baruch, Y. (2006). "Career Development in Organizations and Beyond: Balancing Traditional and Contemporary Viewpoints", *Human Resources Management Review*, Vol. 16, pp. 125-138.
- [11] Benedicta E. & Appiah April, (2010), "The impact of training on employee performance: A Case Study of HFC Bank (GHANA) Ltd". Pp. 15-17
- [12] Byrne, S. M. (2009) the Value of Human Resources Development to an Organization: Providing Technical Assistance to Small Manufacturing Companies. Unpublished Ph.D thesis of Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University.
- [13] Chiaburu, D. S. & Teklab, A. G. (2005). Individual and Contextual Influences on Multiple Dimensions of Training Effectiveness. *Journal of European Industrial Training. p. 282-290*.
- [14] Cole, G. A. (2002). "Personnel and Human Resources Management," (5th ed.), Continuum London: York Publishers
- [15] Cooke F L. (2000). "Human Resources Strategy to improve Organizational Performance: A route for British firms", Working Paper No 9 EWERC, Manchester School of Management.
- [16] Dang, D. Y., & Gadi, P. D. (2013). Integrating Leadership And Ethics: Consequences And Implications In Achieving Results In The Private Sector. *International Journal of Education and Research, 1(May)*, 0–10.
- [17] Debrah, Y. A. & Ofori, G. (2006). Human Resources Development of Professionals in an Emerging Economy: the Case of the Tanzanian Construction Industry. *International Journal of Human Resources Management 17, 3, 440 – 463*.
- [18] Dessler, G. (2000). "*Human Resources Management*," Prentice Hall, 8th edition. London.
- [19] Eleve, B. (2012). How Does Training and Development Impact University of Maryland University College.
- [20] Evans, P., Pucik, V. & Barsoux, J. (2002). *The Global Challenge: Frameworks for International Human Resource Management*. New York: McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
- [21] Gadi, P. D., & Kee, D. H. M. (2018a). Human resource management practices and turnover intention : The mediating role of perceived organizational support in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *International Journal of Engineering & Technology, 7(3)*, 715–722. <https://doi.org/10.14419/ijet.v7i3.25.17832>

- [22] Gadi, P. D., & Kee, D. M. H. (2018b). HRM practices , workplace bullying , and turnover intention : The mediating role of employee engagement. In *Asia Proceedings of Social Sciences (APSS)* (Vol. 2, pp. 92–95).
- [23] Gadi, P. D., Silas, G., & Macrop, D. (2015). Staff Development Programs And Job Performance Of Lecturers Of Plateau State Polytechnic Barkin Ladi*. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business Research*, 4(1), 39–48.
- [24] Gareth, M. (2003). “*Contemporary Management*,” New York, American: McGraw-Hill
- [25] Harrison, R. (2000). *Employee Development*, Beekman Publishing, Silver Lakes, Pretoria.
- [26] Harvey, M. (2002). Human Resources Management in Africa: Alice’s Adventures in Wonderland. *International Journal of Human Resources Management*. 13, 7, 1119 – 1145.
- [27] Harvey, M., Myers, M. & Novicevic, M. M. (2002). The Role of MNCs in Balancing the Human Capital “Books” between African and Developed Countries. *International Journal of Human Resources Management*. 13, 7, 1060 – 1076.
- [28] Herman, A. & Kurt, K. (2009). “Benefits of Training and Development for Individuals and Teams, Organizations, and Society”. *Annual Review of Psychology*.60.
- [29] Houger, V. P. (2006). “Trends of Employees Performance: Collaborative Efforts between Manager and Employees,” *Journal of Performance Improvement*, 45(5), 26-31.
- [30] Irene, F. L. (2009). “A Thesis on the Impact of Training and Development on the Worker Performance and Productivity in the Public Sector Organizations: A case study of Ghana Ports and Harbours Authority,” (Submitted Thesis), *Institute of Distance Learning: KNUST*
- [31] Jackson, T. (2002). Reframing Human Resources Management in Africa: A Cross-Cultural Perspective. *International Journal of Human Resources Management* 13, 7, 998–1018.
- [32] Jeremic, Z., Jovanovic, J. & Gasevic, D. (2009). Evaluating an Intelligent Tutoring System for Design Patterns: the DEPTHs Experience *Educational Technology and Society*, 12 (2).
- [33] Jones, M. K., Richard J. J, Paul L. L., & Peter J. S. (2008) “Training, Job Satisfaction and Workplace Performance in Britain: Evidence from WERS 2004,” IZA Discussion Papers 3677, Institut zur Zukunft der Arbeit (IZA).
- [34] Kamoche, K. (2002). Introduction: Human Resources Management in Africa. *International Journal of Human Resources Management* 13, 7, 993–997.
- [35] Kamoche, K., Yaw, D., Frank, H. & Gerry, N. M. (2004) *Managing Human Resources in Africa*. London: Routledge.
- [36] Kim, S. (2006). “Public Service Motivation and Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Korea”, *International Journal of Manpower*, Vol. 26 No. 8, pp. 722-40.
- [37] Kinicki, A. & Kreitner, R. (2007). *Organizational Behavior*, McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
- [38] Kraak, A. (2005). Human Resources Development and the Skills Crisis in South Africa: the Need for Multi-pronged Strategy. *Journal of Education and Work* 18, 1, 57–83.
- [39] Kum, F. D., Cowden, R. & Karodia, A. M. (2014) the Impact of Training and Development on Employee Performance: A Case Study of ESCON Consulting. *Singaporean Journal of Business Economics, and Management Studies* Vol. 3, No.3.
- [40] Lisa, A. B. & Holly, M. H. (2007). *Training Transfer: An Integrative Literature Review*. Retrieved on 17/12/12 from [www.bizlibrary.com/Portals/0/ALIGN_2011/Presentation_Files/Burke and Hutchins Training Transfer BCarnes.pdf](http://www.bizlibrary.com/Portals/0/ALIGN_2011/Presentation_Files/Burke_and_Hutchins_Training_Transfer_BCarnes.pdf).
- [41] McCourt, W. & Derek, E. (2003). *Global Human Resource Management: Managing People in Developing and Transitional Countries*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar.
- [42] Michael, S.O. (2008). Using Motivational Strategy as Panacea for Employee Retention and Turn over in Selected Public and Private sector Organizations in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. Masters in Commerce Thesis, University of Fort Hare.
- [43] Muma, M., Iravo, A. & Omondi, M. (2014). Effect of Training Needs Assessment on Employee Commitment in Public Universities: A Case Study of Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, September 2014. Vol.4, No.9 ISSN: 2222-6990.

- [44] Ngome,C.K. (2010). Massive Growth of University Education in East Africa and the Challenges Facing the sector from 2000 to2010.The case of Kenya IUCEA. Conference, 19th-21st October. Kampala.
- [45] Niazi, A. S. (2011). “Training and Development Strategy and Its Role in Organizational Performance,” *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 1(2), 42-57.
- [46] Obisi, C. (2001). Employee Development, Issues and Dimensions, *Uncial Journal of Public Administration*, Sept. Vol.1
- [47] Purcell, J., Kinnie, N., Hutchinson, S., Rayton, B. & Swart, J. (2003). Understanding the People and Performance Link: Unlocking the Black-Box. Research Report, CIPD, London.
- [48] Quarty, S. H. (2012). Effect of Employee Training on the Perceived Organizational Performance: A Case Study of the Print-Media Industry in Ghana. *European Journal of Business and Management*, ISSN 2222-1905(Paper) ISSN 2222-2839 (Online) Vol.4, No.15.
- [49] Raja, A. G., Furqan, A. K. & Muhammad, A. K. (2011). “Impact of Training and Development on Organizational Performance”, *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*. 11(7).
- [50] Rao, V.S. (2011). “*Human Resources Management: Text and Cases*,” (2nd ed.), Excel Book, New Delhi
- [51] Swart, J., Mann, C., Brown, S. & Price, A. (2005). *Human Resource Development: Strategy and Tactics*, Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann Publications, Oxford.
- [52] Torrington, D., Hall, L. & Taylor, S. (2005) *Human Resources Management*. 6th Ed. London: Prentice Hall
- [53] Wright, P. &Geroy, D. G. (2001) “Changing the Mindset: The Training Myth and the Need for World-Class Performance”, *International Journal of Human Resources Management*, Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 586-600.
- [54] Ying Chu Ng. (2004). Training determinants and Productivity Impact Of Training in China: A Case of Shanghai”, *Economics of Education Review*, Vol; 24, Pp. 275

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